

THE IMPORTANCE OF BUSINESS PROCESS CONTROLLING IN THE BANKING SYSTEM

D.Matniyazova

student of Mamun university

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13822516>

Nowadays, making rational decisions from the economic point of view is directly related to access to reliable and up-to-date management information. Managers must be properly supported in this area. Certainly, properly modelled controlling can play a key role in this respect. However, it should be constantly adapted to what is happening in the environment and in the enterprise itself.

Market changes and increased customer expectations lead to changes in management systems. Business processes are certainly gaining in importance. However, their management cannot be effective without appropriate support by controlling business processes. The aim of the article is to present the role of business process controlling in the enterprise controlling system.

Business process management implies a specific life cycle. The process is first described (documented) and then optimized. The last stage is control of the ongoing business process. Thus, controlling a business process means monitoring process indicators and analysing the structure of the "actual" process, as well as the efficiency of its participants. The loop closes: if the process is measured, it can be improved, that is, sent back to the description and implementation stages.

A clear picture of the operations allows you to set up and better control. An efficient company is a well-organized company. It seems like a trivial statement but it is not, if we define more precisely what the organization entails. For example, define a detailed picture of the operational processes and of each individual workflow that involves the business.

A common starting condition is to have a detailed map of the operation of a company. A compass to navigate costs, time and resources and thus make truly informed decisions in process control.

Each flow represents the starting input, the procedure that involves it and the output it produces. It is a very effective simplification because it allows you to define and quantify the resources involved and the expected results more precisely. A scheme like this, on the other hand, is perfect to be controlled.

As you know, it is impossible to manage what cannot be measured. The control indicators of a product are usually embedded in the process flowchart, but monitoring the performance indicators of the process often remains out of

sight of analysts. For example, the models of most banking processes include control over the amount of credit, but rarely take into account the time spent and ignore the cost of executing operations. As consequence, the process model does not perform corrective actions because it does not control its indicators.

Controlling business processes should be future-oriented, because enterprises constantly compete, operate in a very volatile environment and have to deal with the negative effects of possible crises, therefore in this aspect the entire planning and reporting system in controlling business processes should be adapted to these elements. Thanks to this, it is possible to develop and implement new concepts and tools that provide accurate information about the future development of the company.

Business process controlling should be "actively" involved in: process identification, process measurement, process analysis, process control, process improvement. At the process identification stage, a properly modelled controlling of business processes is mainly intended to support the determination of the requirements of external and internal customers. Based on this information, real processes can be created. Then, in this area of process management, it enables the graphical representation of processes with the exact definition of inputs and outputs and the assignment of specific resources to them. Measurement of processes based on achievements (results) has become a priority in process management, therefore in this respect business process controlling is helpful in determining the best process measures. It also provides multi-slice data so that the selected measures can be easily calculated. It also actively participates in updating the catalog of meters and their possible selection for selected processes. Thanks to the use of business process controlling instruments, it is possible to conduct very complex and advanced process analyses based on specific measures. With their help, the purpose of such analysis is also established. Measures and methods of analysis are selected for the chosen goal. Controlling business processes in this aspect is mainly intended to provide data for analyses.

Controlling business processes plays a special role in enterprise controlling. By achieving goals, fulfilling functions and fulfilling specific tasks, it can certainly be oriented towards the future, bottlenecks, market, external and internal customer, value chain, risk and value. Controlling business processes can support process management on many levels: process identification, measurement, analysis, control and improvement. It also provides multi-dimensional information to process managers. The special role of business

process controlling in directing the company towards achieving specific business goals cannot be overestimated.

References:

1. Dumas, M., Rosa, L. M., Mendling, J., & Reijers, A. H. (2018). Fundamentals of business process management. Springer-Verlag.
2. Bakberganovich, S. A. (2022). Ways of development of digital economy in the country. Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal, 3(10), 439-442.
3. Dumas, M., La Rosa, M., Mendling, J., Reijers, H. A., Dumas, M., La Rosa, M., ... & Reijers, H. A. (2018). Introduction to business process management. Fundamentals of business process management, 1-33.
4. Шеров, А. Б., & Юнусов, С. Ю. Ў. (2022). Перспективы развития цифровой экономики в Узбекистане. Scientific progress, 3(3), 667-671.
5. Harmon, P. (2019). Business process change: a business process management guide for managers and process professionals. Morgan Kaufmann.
6. Khudoykulov, H. A., & Sherov, A. B. (2021). Digital economy development in corporate governance of joint stock company. Экономика и бизнес: теория и практика, (3-2), 217-219.
7. Шеров, А. Б., & Юсупов, Ш. Б. (2021). Зарубежный опыт эффективной организации денежно-кредитной политики в стране. Scientific progress, 2(1), 605-609.

